

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC RELATIONS IN THE NAMES OF WORKING WEAPONS

S.S.No'monova

Andijan state university Interfaculty foreign languages (exact and natural sciences) senior teacher of the department (independent researcher)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7847859>

Annotation: In this article is written on the basis of the theme of lexical and semantic relations in the names of tools, and is divided into categories depending on their meanings and types, what tasks they perform in the process of labor. In particular, in our linguistics, the names of tools are not divided into motivated and unmotivated, the semantics of their motivated names have not been studied at all, the cognitive aspects of the semantics of the names of tools have not been studied, the categorical approach to the motivated names of tools was not used. In addition, attention was drawn to the similarities and differences of Uzbek and English tools.

Key words: means of labor, lexical and semantic, category, approach, similar, different, task, motivated, need.

Introduction

Due to the development of technology in the 20th-21st centuries, which led to the emergence of many new names of labor tools, the need to study their structure and semantics within the category is increasing. Forms of thought, as well as categories, which are stable organizational principles of the thinking process, reproduce the properties and relations of being and knowledge in a general and most concentrated form. This applies to all categories, including the derivative category of labor tools. It is not an exaggeration to say that the semantic, structural and cognitive characteristics of the names of labor tools, which are considered within the framework of a complex word formation unit such as the category of word formation, form the basis of this article. The main importance of the article is to identify and describe the specific structural, semantic, and cognitive features of the word-forming group of names of labor tools in the development of the typology of substantive naming tools in the aspect of word formation.

The main part.

In general, the names of tools of labor have not been systematically studied in Uzbek linguistics. Only some word-forming forms characteristic of the names of working tools are described. In particular, in our linguistics, the names of labor tools are not divided into motivated and unmotivated, the semantics of their motivated names have not been studied at all, the cognitive aspects of the semantics of the names of labor tools have not been studied, and a categorical approach to the motivated names of labor tools has not been applied [1].

In the article, Uzbek and English labor tools and their tasks were analyzed. For example, the function of the Uzbek word hoe is understandable for Uzbeks, but a foreigner needs to describe the function of this tool. Basically, "In Central Asia: a type of hoe for planting crops, digging ditches, etc." [2]. The word-forming category of the names of working tools has been

studied, and we have given the names of some of them along with the concepts of the word-forming category. For example, we have given the definition of an agricultural tool that is necessary in a farm, for plowing between rows in the fields - this is a labor tool (employer). A scraper is a sharp knife for scraping or cleaning something. This tool performs the same task in both English and Uzbek languages, but differs in both languages in terms of its form and semantic content. The lexical composition of nouns naming tools is dynamic and has different names, but the semantic element "tool" is a mandatory, integral feature for each lexeme belonging to this category. Tools are a permanent part of the semantic structure of the names of work tools, we understand it as an object, device, tool, device for performing any work. With this understanding of the semantic element "tools", the group of word formation of tools includes additional lexemes of the following groups:[3]

- a) names of some objects that act as tools in some cases;
- b) names of some devices - specially created devices;
- c) names of all tools - hand tools;
- d) names of all tools and equipment - technical;
- e) technological machines (machine tools) [4]

Most of the names of working tools are terms - the names of objects for special purposes have a wide scope and are equally understandable to everyone. This is due to the active development of technology, the increase in the level of culture of the population, the popularization of scientific discoveries, and the specific motivation of vocabulary. All this helps special words enter the general vocabulary.

In the process of writing the article, together with the review of the names of labor tools, we studied the thematic groups: "agricultural tools", "household" tools, "industrial tools". "Agricultural tools", "Household tools", "Industrial tools", the word "instrument" is a common semantic component[5].

Results and analyses.

It is concluded that most of the names of working weapons are derived from terms - the names of objects for special purposes. Many terms - tool names - not only have a wide scope, but are understandable to all of us. This is due to the active development of technology, the increase in the level of culture of the population, the popularization of scientific discoveries, and the specific motivation of vocabulary. All this helps special words enter the general vocabulary. In the process of writing the article, we witnessed that the issue of the composition, structure, semantic, structural, and cognitive features of the word-formation series of the names of labor tools is one of the fields that have been rarely studied by scientists. Some Russian scientists found that work tools were divided into several thematic groups: "agricultural tools", "household tools", "industrial tools". Among the differential themes in the meaning of the names of working tools, the typical repeating theme such as "the structure of the tool" is the most common. The named differential sema is typical for the semantics of the following names of household work tools: Stone - a tool of a certain structure, intended for sharpening something; A knife is a kitchen tool used to cut fruits, vegetables and necessary ingredients [6]. This seme is not represented by any morpheme, it opens at the level of word formation and is expressed as a whole word. Intercategory connections of the names of labor tools in the word formation category are expressed by special cases. The studied category of word formation interacts. Based on the study of one or another semanticization of the types of information indicated in the individual motivated names of

labor tools and summarizing the received observations, we identified the following contradictions within the class of motivated names of labor tools [7].

- 1) tools larger than a person: lifter, digger (digger),
- 1) devices smaller than a person: heating stove, boiler, counter
- 2) complex devices: pasteurizer, reflector, carburetor
- 2) primitive arranged tools: boat (wooden shovel), rivet
tools located freely in the width: punch, fan
- 3) devices installed in width: perforator, devices for mechanized unloading of dumper loads, silencer,
- 4) tools that improve any characteristics of individual parts of a person and increase human capabilities without creating new opportunities in principle: spoon, collector, heater, mixer
- 4) tools that create radically new opportunities by improving any characteristics of individual human organs:
direction finder, loop, lamp
- 5) tools designed for convenience:
mixer, refrigerator, lighter
tools created for human living, studying living space:
digger, cutter
single-function tools: hammer, heater, insulation
- 6) multi-functional tools: reload - tap

Conclusion

Finally, we can say that labor tools, the process of their production, are closely related to movement, and are reflected in the meaning of the lexemes that call them. The word-forming semantics of the names of devices and tools allows the speaker to adopt different semantic roles. The semantic roles of the word are the meanings of the word and indicate the obligatory participants of the described speech situation. In general, the development of the word formation category of the names of labor tools continues in the lexicology of the modern Uzbek language. Initially, the group of names of working tools appeared on the basis of the names of the movement, because the needs of the development of production created the need to name the increasingly numerous tools. Currently, the concept of "working tools" is expanding, characterized by the fact that the semantics of tool names do not have clearly defined boundaries.

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